

Multi-targeted B and Co co-doped bioactive glass for angiogenesis

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ABSTRACT

In tissue regeneration area, vascularization is necessary and important to keep adequate blood supply to maintain the survival and growth of new tissue. Because the diffusion distance of nutrients and oxygen for cell survival is limited to 150-200 μm , the viability of the cells at the center of the scaffold is severely hampered [1]. Generally, the tissue layers on the scaffold surface is not thicker than 5 mm, and in the centre of the scaffold, cell density tends to be low and necrosis may occur [1]. Therefore, appropriate angiogenesis for adequate blood supply is necessary and important. Several biomolecules (vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) [2] and basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) [3]), as well as metal ions (copper (Cu) [4], cobalt (Co) [5], strontium (Sr) [6], magnesium (Mg) [7], B [8] and calcium (Ca) [9]) have been already used to promote angiogenesis. In the area of ions-induced angiogenesis, single ion including Cu, Co, Sr, Mg, B and Ca has been extensively investigated: their effectiveness on angiogenesis was demonstrated [4-9]. In the past decade, B has been increasingly used in bioactive materials to promote angiogenesis, exhibiting positive effect on neovascularization. B potently activates the MAPK signalling pathway to markedly enhance the secretion of VEGF, interleukin 6 (IL-6) and bFGF [8, 10, 11] which as the pro-angiogenic cytokines would stimulate the angiogenic response [12, 13]. Co as an essential element in human physiology can also promote angiogenesis, albeit in a different way. Co^{2+} ion is a well-established chemical inducer of HIF-1 α which elicits a significant hypoxic cascade [14] including VEGF secretion, identified as a key regulator in angiogenesis [15, 16]. It is worth noting that B and Co promote angiogenesis through two different targets: the MAPK signalling pathway and hypoxia pathway. However, the synergy of multi-target on angiogenesis promotion is rarely investigated. Therefore, in this story, B and Co were co-doped bioactive glass in order to verify possible synergistic effect of these elements on angiogenesis promotion through multi-target way.

In first part, the synergy of multi-targeted B and Co were co-doped bioactive glass on angiogenesis promotion was directly investigated. The 45S5 bioactive glass co-doped with B and Co was prepared by conventional melt quenching method: synergistic effect of the two co-doping elements on angiogenesis promotion in two different targets is expected. ATR-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy and inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry were used to characterize the composition, element distribution and ions release of the samples. Results showed that the compositions of all samples are almost consistent with the design, and all elements in samples are homogeneously distributed. Different content of B and Co implies different release rates of these elements. The samples showed bioactivity after immersion in simulated body fluid. The 1% and 0.1% extracts

of all samples did not show any cytotoxicity to MG-63 and ST-2 cells. Compared with single B and Co, B and Co co-doped sample more strongly increases the secretion of vascular endothelial growth factor from ST-2 cells, which supports and confirms the synergistic effect of multi-targeted B and Co co-doping on angiogenesis.

In second part, the tissue engineering scaffold embedding multi-targeted B and Co were co-doped bioactive glass was fabricated for multi-targeted promotion of angiogenesis. The polycaprolactone (PCL) fiber mats embedding multi-targeted B and Co co-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles were fabricated as a tissue regeneration scaffold especially for angiogenesis. B and Co co-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles were successfully prepared with well-defined sphere shape by sol-gel method. B and Co were indeed doped into the nanoparticles. The PCL fiber mats embedding multi-targeted B and Co co-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles were successfully fabricated with clear fibrous and free-beads shape by electrospinning. The Young's moduli of the PCL fiber mats with nanoparticles were similar with the pure PCL fiber mats and suitable to support deformation in scaffolds for soft tissue. The mats also showed a biocompatibility to ST-2 cells. The PCL fiber mats with high content of B and Co promoted the secretion of vascular endothelial growth factor in comparison with the PCL fiber mats with low content of B and Co and without B and Co which demonstrated its potential as a tissue regeneration scaffold material for angiogenesis.

Keywords: multi-target, synergistic effect, angiogenesis, bioactive glass, boron, cobalt, soft tissue regeneration

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